

Complexometric Determination of Palladium(II) in Low Concentrations using 4-Amino-5-Mercapto-3-*n*-Propyl-1,2,4-Triazole as Replacing Reagent

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A simple, rapid, accurate and selective complexometric method is proposed for the determination of palladium(II) Pd(II) with associated diverse metal ions is first complexed with excess EDTA and the uncomplexed EDTA is titrated with zinc sulphate solution in acetic acid-acetate buffer (pH 5.5 to 6.0) till end-point. 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-*n*-propyl-1,2,4-triazole is then added to displace only EDTA from Pd-EDTA complex. The released EDTA is titrated with standard zinc sulphate solution. Reproducible and accurate results are obtained in the concentration range 0.4-5.0 mg of palladium with a relative error less than 0.4%. Interference of many common metal ions is studied. Advantages over other complexometric methods of palladium determination are listed.

It is well known that palladium-EDTA complex can be selectively decomposed using demasking agents such as dimethylglyoxime^{1,2}, benzotriazole³ and 1,10-phenanthroline⁴. These methods are not rapid as they require either heating and/or cooling, or extraction or may involve precipitation during titration, the end-point consequently being not distinct. Dimethylglyoxime method¹ involves titration with Cu(II) sulphate at 50° and also requires the use of CHCl₃ to extract the voluminous precipitate of Pd-DMG complex. Benzotriazole method³ needs heating to 60° for 10 min to demask Pd-EDTA complex and cooling to room temp. before titration. Besides, Pd(II) forms a white precipitate with the reagent and hence the end-point is not sharp. The latest 1,10-phenanthroline method⁴ does not work for Pd(II) in the presence of common metal ions. In this paper, the use and advantages of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-*n*-propyl-1,2,4-triazole (HPAMT) as a selective demasking agent for the complexometric determination of Pd(II) is reported.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. or chemically pure grade of B.D.H.

EDTA (0.01 *M*): Prepared from the disodium salt of EDTA.

Palladium chloride (0.005 *M*): Prepared by dissolving PdCl₂ in excess KCl solution and then standardised by dimethylglyoxime method^{2,5}.

HPAMT (0.005 *M*): The reagent was synthesised by reported method⁶. (Found: C, 38.15; H, 6.17; N, 35.91; S, 20.30. C₈H₁₀N₄S requires C, 37.95; H, 6.37; N, 35.41; S, 20.26%), m.p. 104° and used as a 0.005 *M* solution in acetone.

ZnSO₄ (0.01 *M*): Prepared from ZnSO₄·7H₂O and standardized by the quinaldinate method⁵.

Procedure :

To an aliquot of the neutral solution (containing 0.5 to 5 mg) of Pd(II), an excess of 0.01 *M* EDTA solution is added. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 5.5 and 6 by adding acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. The uncomplexed EDTA is back-titrated against the standard zinc sulphate solution (0.01 *M*) to the sharp colour change of xylenol orange indicator from yellow to red. To this is then added an excess of HPAMT solution (50% excess over the molar ratio of 1 : 2), the contents are mixed well and allowed to stand for 5 min. The liberated EDTA is titrated with 0.01 *M* zinc sulphate solution to the same end-point as before. The second titre value is equivalent to the Pd(II) present in the aliquot.

Results and Discussion

The results of determination of palladium(II) from its solution (Table 1) and from a standard alloy sample (Table 2) show that reproducible and accurate values are obtained with a relative error

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM(II) IN PALLADIUM CHLORIDE SOLUTION

Pd present (mg)	Pd found (mg)	Mean	Relative error (%)
0.441	0.441	0.441	0.00
	0.441		
	0.441		
0.882	0.892	0.885	+0.34
	0.882		
	0.882		
1.323	1.313	1.328	+0.38
	1.336		
	1.335		
2.645	2.646	2.646	+0.04
	2.646		
	2.646		
4.409	4.399	4.402	-0.16
	4.399		
	4.409		

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM IN STANDARD Pd-20% Ni ALLOY (BHN 190)

Pd present* (mg)	Pd found (mg)	Mean	Relative error (%)
0.402	0.405	0.408	0.35
	0.402		
	0.403		
0.804	0.806	0.804	0.00
	0.808		
	0.804		

* Determination from acid solution by the methods under refs. 2 and 5.

of <0.4%. Effect of common metal ions on the quantitative determination of Pd(II) was studied with aliquots containing 0.441 mg of Pd(II). The cations listed in Table 3 show no interference upto

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CATIONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) (Palladium present=0.441 mg)

Ion added	Quantity of ion added (mg)	Palladium found* (mg)	Relative error (%)	Maximum concentration of diverse ion studied with no interference (mg)
Pb(II)	0.7	0.442	+0.23	9.0
Cu(II)	0.9	0.441	0.00	9.0
Cd(II)	0.4	0.444	+0.68	4.4
Co(II)	0.9	0.444	+0.68	9.0
Ni(II)	0.9	0.441	0.00	9.0
Bi(III)	1.1	0.444	+0.68	5.5
Fe(III)	1.3	0.440	-0.23	6.6
Cr(III)	1.8	0.438	-0.68	9.0
Au(III)	0.9	0.438	-0.68	1.8

*Average of two readings.

the limits studied and hence require no secondary masking agents. However, cations like Ag(I), Hg(II), Sn(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Sb(III) and Al(III) show interference but this can be obviated by using appropriate secondary masking agents.

The quantitative displacement of EDTA from Pd-EDTA complex by HPAMT indicates that the Pd-HPAMT complex is more stable than the Pd-EDTA complex at room temp. and that EDTA is released spontaneously. However, for complete release of EDTA, a minimum of 50 percent excess of HPAMT reagent over the stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2 for the metal to reagent is desirable. A large excess of the reagent did not have any adverse effect in the determination.

Advantages: The speciality of the reagent is that it does not form any precipitate with either Pd(II) the metal ion to be estimated, or Zn(II), the titrant, under the experimental conditions. This facilitates sharp detection of the end-point without resorting to the use of other chemicals. The method works well especially at low concentrations of Pd(II) in the range <5 mg.

The main advantage of the proposed method is that it does not require heating or cooling before the titration or for demasking the Pd-EDTA complex. Since the presence of numerous metal ions can be tolerated, the method is suitable for estimation of Pd in certain palladium-alloys. The method does not involve extraction of Pd-complex and hence is economic and can be rapidly carried out in a single stage. The EDTA solution need not be standardised. The method also affords estimation of Pd(II) at milligram level with accurate and reproducible results. Since the titrations are carried out at the same pH, the method requires no re-adjustment of pH.

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References

1. K. N. RAOOT and SARALA RAOOT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 1007.
2. V. N. TIKHONOV and E. A. ALEKSANDROVA, *Zavod. Lab.*, 1977, 43, 922.
3. K. N. RAOOT and SARALA RAOOT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 18A, 90.
4. SARALA RAOOT and K. N. RAOOT, *Indian J. Tech.*, 1980, 18, 345.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", The ELBS and Longman, 1978, 4th Edn., p. 474, 488.
6. K. S. DEAKA, V. K. JAGMOHAN CHADHA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 288.